

Using pValue to Measure Significance Level of Continuous Data

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we provide a practical method on how to calculate pValue for continuous data. In later paper, we will cover pValue for discrete data. For continuous distribution in part 1, we defined pValue as $1 - \text{CDF}$; for discrete distribution in part 2, we define pValue as $1 - \text{MDF}$. The purpose of this paper is to provide a practical guide on how to calculate the pValue if the sample size, and critical value for T or Z are known. The methodology has practical value to researchers in both natural and social science. All quantitative research requires the reporting of statistical significance. The T and Z values are known in the field. We claim new discovery for the method on how to calculate pValue through the TZ conversion equation. We proposed three steps in calculating pValue: (i) converting chi square or F to T, (ii) with known T, obtain Z by using the TZ conversion equation $Z = (1.15T - 1.64) + 1.40$, and (iii) with known Z, determine $F(Z)$. The pValue is simply $1 - F(Z)$. This procedure is a contribution to the field because it serves as an effective tool for editorial and peer reviews in research publication. We present three tables for converting test statistics T, chi square, and F to pValue.

Keyword: error level, pValue, significance level

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

In research publications, pValue is generated by computer software. It is never reported as a result of a manual calculation. Thus, in peer or editorial review, the reported pValue is taken at face value. The purpose of this paper is to provide a manual calculation method of how to determine pValue. Despite suggestions made by some writers to use other methods for reporting significance level, pValue remains a common indicator to report.

In finding the significance level for hypothesis testing, the researcher begins with a threshold against which the observed value is compared. For example, if the researcher uses 95%

confidence interval, the error level is 5%. pValue is the measurement of the error level. It answers the question of “what is the error level?” In answering this question, the standard decision rule is that the finding is not significant if the error level is larger than 5%, i.e. $p > 0.05$. In such a case, the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. If the error level is equal to or less than 5% or $p \leq 0.05$, the null hypothesis is rejected. In sum, the significance level is the pValue; the pValue is the error level.

When reporting pValue, authors tend to describe whether the value is for one or two tails. In this paper, we do not explain pValue in terms of the “tails.” The significance level or the alpha region of the distribution curve comes from a unit circle; that circle is divided into two regions, namely 95% confidence interval and the remaining 5% random error regions all round the edge of the circle. In essence, the circle has no tail. Thus, it is an error to assert that for a 5% error level, the upper and lower tail has 2.5% error level each. If 2.5% error level is used, the confidence interval becomes 97.5%, not 95%. Fig. 1 helps illustrate this point.

Fig. 1. Transforming 3D elliptical sphere to a unit circle and half circle

In Fig. 1, the data cloud is represented by the sphere. The black dots inside the sphere represent data points (Picture A). To facilitate easy comprehension, the 3D model is simplified into 2D model of a unit circle (Picture B). This 2D model, the circle is divided into two regions: 95% confidence non-significance region (white) and 5% error region or significance level (shaded). This 2D model is further simplified by removing one half of the circle (Picture C). What remains is the half circle with two regions divided evenly all round maintaining the distance of 95% and 5%. Thus, the concept of “upper tail” and “lower tail” is an inaccurate description of the half-circle which we call the distribution curve. In this paper, when we refer to the 5% error (alpha region) level, it is 5% not the so-called 2.5% “one-tail.”

The purpose of this paper is to provide a meaningful and practical guide for manually calculating the pValue. Although statistical software programs provide pValue as an automatic calculation, it is worth knowing how that value is calculated. For editorial or peer review purpose, knowing the method of calculating the pValue helps facilitate the evaluation of research findings.

What is the pValue? pValue is the significance level. It is the error level determined by $1 - F(Z)$ where $F(Z)$ is the cumulative distribution function (CDF) or the area under the distribution curve. In this paper, we assume the normal distribution curve as a reference curve. The reading of the pValue is the reading of the random error region on the distribution curve. If the error level or the result of $1 - F(Z)$ is less than the predetermined error level, i.e. 5% in a 95% confidence interval then the finding is statistically significant. If the observed error level ($1 - F(Z)$) is greater than 5% then the finding is statistically not significant.

The alternative reading is the critical value (Z) or the percentage probability of the event or $F(Z)$. In the pValue reading, the error level is set as the threshold level; however, in the alternative reading, the critical score or the percentage probability is used by comparing the observed to the threshold value. For instance, in a 95% confidence interval, the null hypothesis of non-significance

is rejected if the observed $F(Z)$ is equal to or greater than 95% or $F(Z) \geq 0.95$. If the critical value is used, then the value of the observed test statistic Z is used. For 95% confidence interval, the threshold value is 1.65. Note that for 95% confidence interval, the critical value for Z is not 1.97; at $Z = 1.97$, the percentage probability is 97.5%, not 95%. As shown in Fig. 1, the 5% error is all round the edge of the circle; there is no upper or lower tail. The error level is 5% equi-distance all round the edge of the circle.

2.0 LITERATURE

pValue is used in many fields of research (Bhaskar and DeSale, 2002), both in the natural and social sciences (Wetzels *et al.*, 2001). Depending on the field of research, the pValue may range from 1% to 5% (Nuzzo, 2014). In social science, a 5% level is generally used. In the natural science, using 1% pValue is common. However, a pValue reading of 1% or less may be a false alarm reading (Goodman, 2001). Thus, it is important to know how to verify the calculation.

There had been evidence of the misuse and misunderstanding of pValue. It has been misunderstood that it means the null hypothesis *cannot* be rejected (Colquhoun, 2014). There had been attempts to propose alternative means to reject the null hypothesis other than by using the pValue. One proposed alternative is the use of confidence interval (Lee, 2017; Ranstam, 2012). However, confidence interval reading is not much difference than pValue because confidence interval is $F(Z)$ and the pValue is $1 - F(Z)$. The confidence interval is not an alternative to pValue; it is one step less in the calculation, but not an alternative. It has also been suggested that a fixed pValue be removed and the pValue be used as a continuous indices to indicate the strength of evidence against the null hypothesis (Arhein *et al.*, 2017; Arhein and Greenland, 2017). Arhein's suggestion is an alternative reading of pValue, not an alternative method to pValue.

pValue is not the final criterion for rejecting the null hypothesis, there must also be other supporting evidence (Goodman, 1999; Wasserstein and Lazar, 2016). For instance, effect size (Cohen, 1988; Cohen, 1992). Standardized means and odds ratio may be used to measure effect size (Hedges and Olkin, 1985; p. 369). Correlation coefficient is a common measure for effect size (Britten, 1996; Moller and Thornhill, 1998; Reed and Frankham, 2001; Koricheva, 2002; Rosenthal and Rubin, 1978).

Effect size is the measure of the magnitude of the phenomenon (Kelley and Preacher, 2012). It considered a good research practice to report the effect size (Wilkinson; 1999; Nakagawa and Cuthill, 2007). The APA Task Force on Statistical Inference urged that:

“Always present effect sizes for primary outcomes...If the units of measurement are meaningful on a practical level (e.g., number of cigarettes smoked per day), then we usually prefer an unstandardized measure (regression coefficient or mean difference) to a standardized measure (r or d).”—L. Wilkinson and APA Task Force on Statistical Inference (1999, p. 599).

The problem with the effect size measurement is that it gives the reading in a critical value form, not on the probability space such as the confidence interval ($F(Z)$) or the pValue ($1 - F(Z)$). For instance, the effect size under the Cohen d method, the result of the test statistic is not readily readable in percentage probability format. The Cohen's d is given by:

$$d = \frac{\bar{X}_1 - \bar{X}_2}{S} = \frac{\mu_1 - \mu_2}{S} \quad (1)$$

where $S = \sqrt{\frac{(n_1 - 1)S_1^2 + (n_2 - 1)S_2^2}{n_1 + n_2 - 2}}$ (Cohen, 1998, p. 67); other authors suggest removing -2 from the denominator of the pool variance (McGrath and Meyer, 2006; Hartung, 2008, p.14). The

evaluation of the value of d was provided by Sawilowsky (Sawilowsky, 2009; pp.467-474) as a range from 0.01 (very small), 0.20 (small), 0.50 (medium), 0.80 (large), 1.20 (very large), and 2.0 (huge). These adjectives describing the magnitude of the effect are not meaningful because the Cohen's d actually mimics the standard score equation: $z = (x_i - \bar{x}) / s$ where the percentage probability $F(Z)$ may be obtained, likewise the Cohen's d is a functional equivalence of reading the z score without going another step of finding $F(Z)$ from which the pValue may be calculated by: $1 - F(Z)$.

Although the effect size is recommended for reporting the findings, nevertheless, pValue remains the most commonly used indicators for rejecting the null hypothesis because the pValue speaks in percentage probability of the error term or the error level measured in percentage form. Since pValue is generated by software program and there is no easy manual method for calculating the pValue unless, the three steps process we introduced in this paper fills the gap in the literature.

3.0 DATA FOR ILLUSTRATION

3.1 Data used

For purposes of illustration, we use the percentage change of GDP and percentage change of export volume of 10 countries in ASEAN for a period of 5 years: 2010 – 2014. This secondary data was obtained from the IMF's annual report of World Economic Outlook 2017. In the example, we assume that export contributes to the GDP and will test this assumption by a linear equation:

$$Y_{gdp} = a + bX_{exp}.$$

Table 1. Percentage change in GDP* of 10 countries in ASEAN from 2008 to 2017

Country	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
1*	0.18	(0.26)	0.15	0.35	0.03	(0.05)	(0.05)	(0.24)	(0.12)	0.12
2	0.20	-	0.08	0.14	0.10	0.09	0.10	0.09	0.11	0.10
3	0.19	0.03	0.31	0.18	0.03	-	0.03)	0.03)	0.08	0.09
4	0.25	0.08	0.17	0.19	0.14	0.17	0.11	0.08	0.11	0.07
5	0.19	0.12)	0.22	0.17	0.06	0.03	0.05	(0.12)	-	0.06
6	0.48	0.10	0.30	0.21	-	0.01	0.09	(0.09)	0.06	0.05
7	0.16	0.03)	0.18	0.12	0.12	0.09	0.05	0.03	0.04	0.03
8	0.07	-	0.23	0.17	0.05	0.05	0.02	(0.02)	0.02	0.05
9	0.11	0.03)	0.21	0.09	0.07	0.06	0.03)	(0.01)	0.03	0.11
10	0.27	0.03	0.11	0.19	0.16	0.10	0.09	0.03	0.05	0.09

*The 10 countries are: Brunei, Cambodia, Indonesia, Laos, Malaysia, Myanmar, Philippines, Singapore, Thailand, and Vietnam.

Source: <https://www.imf.org/external/pubs/ft/weo/2017/02/weodata/index.aspx>

The GDP patterns are presented in Fig. 1. Among the 10 ASEAN countries, Myanmar and Cambodia show the highest level of percentage change in annual GDP while the remaining 8 countries are in the lower level. We will later test whether this apparent group difference is significant by calculating the pValue of their difference. The test statistic for the difference will be obtained by:

$$T = \frac{(\bar{X}_1 - \bar{X}_2) - (\mu_1 - \mu_2)}{S \sqrt{\frac{1}{n_1} + \frac{1}{n_2}}} \quad (2)$$

where S is the pool standard deviation determined by:

$$S_{pool} = \sqrt{\frac{(n_1 - 1)S_1^2 + (n_2 - 1)S_2^2}{n_1 + n_2 - 2}} \quad (3)$$

Once we obtained T in (2), we will follow equations (9) and (10) to obtain the pValue to verify whether the two groups of countries are significantly different in their GDP.

Fig. 2. Patterns of percentage change of GDP for ASEAN countries: 2008 – 2017

The percentage change of annual GDP is defined as the dependent variable (DV). The independent variable (IV) is percentage change of annual export. The export data for 10 countries over a period of 10 years (2008 – 2017) is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Percentage change of export of 10 countries in ASEAN from 2008 to 2017

Country	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
1	(7.05)	(6.66)	11.71	(4.58)	(2.80)	(9.28)	4.32	(13.77)	(1.89)	(1.98)
2	2.18	(4.96)	33.85	5.85	5.98	6.35	13.85	12.64	4.51	0.83
3	(2.95)	5.61	3.43	6.69	1.85	3.05	1.63	0.08	0.69)	5.56
4	3.66	4.88	16.73	1.67	6.69	0.62	22.08	(4.80)	0.53	6.10
5	7.30)	10.47)	3.62	6.26	6.49)	0.07	6.50	4.05	3.63	8.22
6	0.01	12.89	10.30	9.63	4.86	5.36	9.49	(0.11)	3.44	7.18
7	2.21)	(5.87)	19.86	0.69)	5.97	3.72	11.52	0.44	4.99	11.38
8	4.84	(7.66)	17.44	6.67	1.70	5.95	3.36	4.74	1.11	4.10
9	6.26	12.14)	14.22	9.51	4.88	2.72	0.26	1.57	2.79	6.59
10	2.13	3.74	6.58	4.13	5.59	6.94	10.98	9.77	0.74	15.85

Source: <https://www.imf.org/external/pubs/ft/weo/2017/02/weodata/index.aspx>

In Fig. 1, we saw patterns of the percentage change in GDP for the 10 countries over the 10 years period. That patterns show the 10 countries moving in the same direction in a tighter formation. In contrast, the patterns of the percentage export change in Fig. 2, the pattern is less uniform. Export growth patterns among the countries are more diverse. The issue of pattern recognition and trend testing is beyond the scope of this paper. This cursory visual observation points to a possible research issue worth exploring.

Fig. 3. Patterns of percentage change in export for ASEAN countries: 2008 - 2017

The hypothesis we wanted to test is whether export significantly contributes to the GDP? There are three steps in this verification. Firstly, there is a relationship between export and the GDP or $Y_{gdp} = a + bX_{exp}$; in this first step, it is necessary to prove that the relationship between X and Y exists by showing that $b \neq 0$. Second, determining the intensity of that relationship by calculating the correlation coefficient r by $r = b(S_x / S_y)$; and third, obtain the test statistic under the T equation: $T_r = A / B$ where $A = r\sqrt{n-2}$ and $B = \sqrt{1-r^2}$. With known T, we then used equations 9 and 10 to determined the pValue.

4.0 METHODOLOGY

4.1 Converting chi square to T

There are two steps in converting chi square to T. First, chi square is expressed in terms of correlation coefficient. Second, the correlation coefficient is extracted from the T equation in the test statistic for correlation coefficient. These two steps are illustrated below.

$$r = \sqrt{\frac{\chi_1^2}{n}} \quad (4)$$

where r = correlation coefficient; χ_1^2 = chi square with $df = 1$, and n = sample size. To write the equation in terms of chi square, we obtain: $\chi_1^2 = r^2(n)$. In the second step, we obtain the T value by:

$$T_r = \frac{r\sqrt{n-2}}{\sqrt{1-r^2}} \quad (5)$$

After chi square is converted to T, use equations 9 and 10 to convert T to pValue.

Chi square may be converted to correlation coefficient by taking the square root of the quotient of chi square ($df = 1$) divided by the sample size (Cohen, 1965). Using chi square with

degree of freedom 1 is the most simplest form, larger degree of freedom makes the process more complicated (Rosenthal *et al.*, 2000).

In case where we deal with the observed chi square that has large degree of freedom, we proposed the following procedure: (i) convert the chi square observed to chi square with $df = 1$, and (ii) used equation 4 to process chi square to r as in equation (4). The chi square conversion may be obtained by:

$$\chi^2 = \frac{1}{n_1 + n_2 - 2} \left(\frac{(\chi_o^2 - \chi_e^2)^2}{\chi_e^2} \right) \tag{6}$$

where χ_e^2 is the chi square value at $df = 1$ and χ_o^2 is the observed chi squared with $df > 1$. Put the result of equation (6) into equation (4) to determine the value of r .

4.2 Converting F to T

Where there are more than one chi square distributed data, the test statistic is the F test. The F test verifies the ratio of the variance of the two data sets. In order to convert the F statistic to pValue, it is necessary to convert F to T first. The T equation is given by:

$$T = \frac{X - \bar{X}}{S / \sqrt{n}} \tag{7}$$

The F test is the ratio of the variance; thus, the equivalence of F and T is given by:

$$F = \left(\frac{X - \bar{X}}{S / \sqrt{n}} \right)^2 \tag{8}$$

This ratio works out to be $F = T^2$. To express T in terms of F then $T = \sqrt{F}$. After F is converted to T, use equations 9 and 10 to convert T to pValue.

As F statistic increases linearly, the pValue decreases in a begative log pattern. As F becomes larger, pValue approaches zero. This behavior is similar to our description of the pValue in chi square (Fig. 4). Recall that F statistic is a test statistic for two samples that are chi square distributed. Thus, the graphic representation of the F statistic vis-à-vis pValue is similar to that observed in the chi square case.

In multiple regression ANOVA where $F = MSR \div MSE$, the equivalabce between F and T by $T = \sqrt{F}$ is also used. Note that generally in multiple regression ANOVA, the strength of the proposed model is measured by R squared. R squared measures the explanatory power of the proposed model, this measure is not the same as pValue. pValue measures the significance or the probability of not occurring, not how many percent can the proposed model explain the data.

4.3 Determining the pValue in three steps

We propose the conversion of T to pValue in three steps. First, with known T a bridge of T to Z must be constructed. This is accomplished by:

$$Z = (1.15T - 1.64) + 1.40 \tag{9}$$

where Z = critical value; T = Student T score, and n = sample size. Equation (9) is a new discovery in T-to-Z conversion method introduced by this paper for the first time. In the second step, with known Z critical value, the percentage probability may be determined by:

$$F(Z) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp\left(-\sqrt{\pi}\left(\beta_1 Z^5 + \beta_2 Z^3 + \beta_3 Z\right)\right)} \quad (10)$$

where $\beta_1 = 0.0004406$, $\beta_2 = 0.0418198$, and $\beta_3 = 0.90000000$. In the third step, the pValue is obtained by $1 - F(Z)$ which is the percentage error or the significance level or alpha level (α) in the distribution curve. For negative Z value, the pValue is obtained by: $1 - (1 - (F(Z)))$.

5.0 FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

We present our findings in two parts. In 5.1, we present findings of pValue for nonparametric case. In 5.2, we present findings pValue in parametric case where the linear regression for the percentage change in GDP (Y) and export (X) are used as variables.

5.1 Non-parametric testing for pValue using the standard score method

In Figs. 1 and 2 we present the raw data for percentage change in the annual GDP and percentage change in export volume from 2008 to 2017. By visual impression, Fig. 1 shows that the percentage change of the GDP has a predictable pattern. This pattern is less obvious in the percentage change of export volume shown in Fig. 2. We test both data sets for their pValue by using the standard score equation and presented their results in Tables 3 and 4.

Table 3. pValue of percentage change in GDP under non-parametric testing

Country	Country Mean	ASEAN Mean	ASEAN SD	Country Z	Country F(Z)	pValue 1 – F(Z)
Brunei	(0.02)	0.08	0.07	(1.41)	0.0780	0.92
Cambodia	0.07	0.08	0.07	(0.11)	0.4545	0.55
Indonesia	0.06	0.08	0.07	(0.36)	0.3606	0.64
Laos	0.08	0.08	0.07	0.03	0.5114	0.49
Malaysia	0.03	0.08	0.07	(0.77)	0.2202	0.78
Myanmar	0.05	0.08	0.07	(0.41)	0.3394	0.66
Philippines	0.05	0.08	0.07	(0.50)	0.3086	0.69
Singapore	0.03	0.08	0.07	(0.67)	0.2510	0.75
Thailand	0.04	0.08	0.07	(0.57)	0.2839	0.72
Vietnam	0.06	0.08	0.07	(0.26)	0.3986	0.60

There is no significant growth of the GDP over the 10 years period for each country using the ASEAN group as a reference. The pValue for all countries' percentage change in GDP are: $0.60 < p < 0.92$.

We also examined the percentage change of export for the 10 countries over a period of 10 years using ASEAN group mean and standard deviation as reference points. The pValue range is $0.13 < p < 0.88$. No country experience significant change in export volume growth.

Table 4. pValue of percentage change in export under non-parametric testing

Country	Country Mean	ASEAN Mean	ASEAN SD	Country Z	Country F(Z)	pValue 1 – F(Z)
Brunei	(0.03)	0.06	0.07	(1.19)	0.1159	0.88

Cambodia	0.14	0.06	0.07	1.14	0.8723	0.13
Indonesia	0.02	0.06	0.07	(0.44)	0.3315	0.67
Laos	0.11	0.06	0.07	0.69	0.7559	0.24
Malaysia	0.01	0.06	0.07	(0.65)	0.2565	0.74
Myanmar	0.08	0.06	0.07	0.36	0.6388	0.36
Philippines	0.04	0.06	0.07	(0.19)	0.4232	0.58
Singapore	0.04	0.06	0.07	(0.19)	0.4232	0.58
Thailand	0.04	0.06	0.07	(0.27)	0.3940	0.61
Vietnam	0.10	0.06	0.07	0.54	0.7039	0.30

5.2 Parametric testing for pValue using linear regression

For parametric testing, we examined the relationship between export and GDP and calculated the pValue for the relationship. The results show that there are 3 countries where the percentage change in export significantly contributed to the GDP; these countries include: Philippines, Singapore and Thailand. There are 7 countries where the percentage change in export does not significantly contribute to the growth of the GDP; these countries include: Brunei, Cambodia, Indonesia, Laos, Malaysia, Myanmar, and Vietnam.

Table 5. Relationship between GDP and export

Country	Linear Eq.	r	T	Z	F(Z)	pValue
Brunei	$Y = -0.42 + 0.59X$	0.43	1.34	1.30	0.9033	0.0967
Cambodia	$Y = -0.16 + 0.13X$	0.43	1.36	1.32	0.9070	0.0930
Indonesia	$Y = -0.17 + 0.39X$	0.36	1.09	1.01	0.8437	0.1563
Laos	$Y = 7.83 + 0.03X$	0.22	0.63	0.48	0.6842	0.3158
Malaysia	$Y = -0.08 + 0.12X$	0.13	0.36	0.18	0.5707	0.4293
Myanmar	$Y = 1.59 + 0.42X$	0.49	1.59	1.59	0.9448	0.0552
Philippines	$Y = 3.53 + 0.17X$	0.91	6.13	6.81	1.0000	- *
Singapore	$Y = 0.38 + 0.69X$	0.81	3.92	4.27	1.0000	0.0000*
Thailand	$Y = 2.71 + 0.35X$	0.59	2.08	2.15	0.9854	0.0146*
Vietnam	$Y = 5.89 + 0.03X$	0.10	0.28	0.09	0.5344	0.4656

*Significant $p \leq 0.05$.

For purposes of procedural illustration, we select one country with significant finding for export growth contributing to the GDP: Philippines. Philippines has a predictive function for export to GDP as: $Y = 3.53 + 0.17X$. From this equation the slope of the linear regression line is $b = 0.17$. The standard deviation for export growth was $S_x = 8.44$ and the standard deviation for the GDP growth was $S_y = 1.58$. The correlation coefficient is calculated by $r = b(S_x / S_y) = 0.17(8.44 / 1.58) = 0.91$. Using the T equation for the test statistic: $T = A \div B$ where $A = r\sqrt{n-2}$ and $B = \sqrt{1-r^2}$; the calculation is $A = 0.91\sqrt{10-2} = 2.57$ and $B = \sqrt{1-0.91^2} = 0.41$. Thus, $T = 2.57 \div 0.41 = 6.21$. The value of T is converted to Z by $Z = (1.15T - 1.64) + 1.40$ or $Z = ((1.15)(1.36) + 1.40$ or $Z = 6.81$. With a critical value of $Z = 6.81$, the percentage probability is obtained by using equation 10, the result is $F(Z) = 10000$. The pValue is obtained by $1 - 1.0000 = 0.0000$. The threshold level for error is 0.05; since 0.0000 is less than 0.05, the pValue is statistically significant.

We illustrate a non-significant case by using Vietnam. The regression equation for Vietnam is $Y = 5.89 + 0.03X$. The slope is $b = 0.03$; the standard deviations are $S_x = 5.39$ and $S_y = 1.62$. The correlation coefficient is $r = b(S_x / S_y) = 0.03(5.39/1.62) = 0.10$. The test statistic is obtained by $T = A \div B$ where $A = 0.10\sqrt{10-2} = 0.28$ and $B = \sqrt{1-0.10^2} = 0.99$; thus, $T = 0.28 \div 0.99 = 0.28$. The value of T is converted to Z by $Z = (1.15(0.28) - 1.64) + 1.40 = 0.09$. Use equation (9) to obtain the percentage probability, the result is $F(Z) = 0.5344$ and pValue for Vietnam is $1 - 0.5344$

= 0.4656. Since 0.4656 is larger than 0.05, Vietnam's percentage change in export does not significantly contribute to the percentage change in the GDP.

As a group, ASEAN's general prediction function for the relationship between percentage change in export and percentage change in GDP is: $Y = 0.04 + 0.003X$. The slope of the line is 0.003 and the standard deviations are: $S_x = 5.02$ and $S_y = 0.02$. The correlation coefficient $r = b(S_x/S_y)$ is 0.71. The test statistic is $T = 2.81$. using equations (9), we convert T to Z by $Z = ((1.15(2.81) - 1.64) + 1.40)$; the result is $Z = 3.00$. using equation (10), we determine the percentage probability to be $F(Z) = 0.9990$ thus, the pValue is $1 - 0.9990$ or 0.0010. We conclude that the percentage change in export significantly contribute to the percentage change in the annual GDP.

Recall that table 5 shows 3 out of 10 countries had significant export contributed to the GDP; it may be inferred that the volume of export of these three economies in ASEAN may have been substantial to have contributed to a condition of "export-led" GDP growth for the ASEAN group.

6.0 CONCLUSION

The intended contribution of this paper is the practical guide for determining pValue. All quantitative research publications are required to report the significance level. pValue is the significance or error level. Throughout this paper, the pValue or error level is fixed at 5% in a 95% confidence interval. We introduce the conversion process in three simple steps: (i) converting chi square or F to T, (ii) with known T, used the bridging equation to convert T to Z by $Z = (1.15T - 1.64) + 1.40$, and (iii) with known Z, determine $F(Z)$. The pValue is simply $1 - F(Z)$. These three steps may be accomplished with manual calculation without any aid of computer software. In addition, these three easy steps will help facilitate editorial or peer reviews in verifying the pValue in research any article in natural or social science. We have tabulated four tables for pValued based on the T, Z, chi square and F statistics. These tables are presented in Appendices 1, 2, 3, and 4.

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APPENDIX 1
pValue from T Statistic

Assume that $T = 1.15X$ then $Z = (1.15T - 1.64) + 1.40$. In the second step, find $f(Z)$ by

$$F(Z) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp\left(-\sqrt{\pi}\left(\beta_1 Z^5 + \beta_2 Z^3 + \beta_3 Z\right)\right)}$$

where $\beta_1 = 0.0004406$, $\beta_2 = 0.0418198$, and $\beta_3 =$

0.90000000. Obtain pValue by $1 - F(Z)$.

T	Z	F(Z)	pValue = 1 - F(Z)
-	(0.24)	0.4052	0.5948
0.10	(0.13)	0.4503	0.5497
0.20	(0.01)	0.4960	0.5040
0.30	0.11	0.5418	0.4582
0.40	0.22	0.5870	0.4130
0.50	0.34	0.6311	0.3689
0.60	0.45	0.6736	0.3264
0.70	0.57	0.7139	0.2861
0.80	0.68	0.7517	0.2483
0.90	0.80	0.7867	0.2133
1.00	0.91	0.8187	0.1813
1.10	1.03	0.8475	0.1525
1.20	1.14	0.8732	0.1268
1.30	1.26	0.8957	0.1043
1.40	1.37	0.9152	0.0848
1.50	1.49	0.9319	0.0681
1.64	1.65	0.9510	0.0490
1.70	1.72	0.9577	0.0423
1.80	1.83	0.9673	0.0327
1.90	1.95	0.9751	0.0249
2.00	2.06	0.9813	0.0187

2.10	2.18	0.9862	0.0138
2.20	2.29	0.9900	0.0100
2.30	2.41	0.9928	0.0072
2.40	2.52	0.9950	0.0050
2.50	2.64	0.9965	0.0035
2.60	2.75	0.9976	0.0024
2.70	2.87	0.9984	0.0016
2.80	2.98	0.9990	0.0010
2.90	3.10	0.9994	0.0006
3.00	3.21	0.9996	0.0004
3.10	3.33	0.9998	0.0002
3.20	3.44	0.9999	0.0001
3.30	3.56	0.9999	0.0001
3.40	3.67	1.0000	0.0000
3.50	3.79	1.0000	0.0000
3.60	3.90	1.0000	0.0000
3.70	4.02	1.0000	0.0000
3.80	4.13	1.0000	0.0000
3.90	4.25	1.0000	0.0000
4.00	4.36	1.0000	0.0000

APPENDIX 2

pValue from Z Statistic

With known +Z, obtain F(Z) by $F(Z) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp\left(-\sqrt{\pi}\left(\beta_1 Z^5 + \beta_2 Z^3 + \beta_3 Z\right)\right)}$ where $\beta_1 =$

0.0004406, $\beta_2 = 0.0418198$, and $\beta_3 = 0.90000000$. Obtain pValue by $1 - F(Z)$ where the value of Z ranges from 0 to +4. With known -Z, obtain F(Z) by $(1 - (1 - F(Z)))$ where the value of Z ranges from 0 to -4:

$F(Z) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp\left(-\sqrt{\pi}\left(\beta_1 Z^5 + \beta_2 Z^3 + \beta_3 Z\right)\right)}$ where $\beta_1 = 0.0004406$, $\beta_2 = 0.0418198$, and $\beta_3 = 0.90000000$.

Z	F(Z)	pValue = 1 - F(Z)
(4.00)	1.0000	0.0000
(3.85)	0.0000	1.0000
(3.70)	0.0000	1.0000
(3.55)	0.0001	0.9999
(3.40)	0.0002	0.9998
(3.25)	0.0003	0.9997
(3.10)	0.0006	0.9994
(2.95)	0.0011	0.9989
(2.80)	0.0020	0.9980
(2.65)	0.0033	0.9967
(2.50)	0.0054	0.9946
(2.35)	0.0084	0.9916
(2.20)	0.0129	0.9871
(2.05)	0.0192	0.9808
(1.90)	0.0277	0.9723

(1.75)	0.0391	0.9609
(1.60)	0.0540	0.9460
(1.45)	0.0729	0.9271
(1.30)	0.0963	0.9037
(1.15)	0.1247	0.8753
(1.00)	0.1585	0.8415
(0.85)	0.1976	0.8024
(0.70)	0.2420	0.7580
(0.55)	0.2912	0.7088
(0.40)	0.3446	0.6554
(0.25)	0.4013	0.5987
(0.10)	0.4602	0.5398
-	0.5000	0.5000
0.05	0.5199	0.4801
0.20	0.5792	0.4208
0.35	0.6368	0.3632
0.50	0.6914	0.3086
0.65	0.7421	0.2579
0.80	0.7882	0.2118
0.95	0.8291	0.1709
1.10	0.8646	0.1354
1.25	0.8948	0.1052
1.40	0.9198	0.0802
1.55	0.9402	0.0598
1.70	0.9563	0.0437
1.85	0.9688	0.0312
2.00	0.9783	0.0217
2.15	0.9852	0.0148
2.30	0.9902	0.0098
2.45	0.9937	0.0063
2.60	0.9961	0.0039
2.75	0.9976	0.0024
2.90	0.9986	0.0014
3.05	0.9992	0.0008
3.20	0.9996	0.0004
3.35	0.9998	0.0002
3.50	0.9999	0.0001
3.65	1.0000	0.0000
3.80	1.0000	0.0000
3.95	1.0000	0.0000
4.00	1.0000	0.0000

APPENDIX 3
pValue from Chi Square Statistic

First convert chi square to r by $r = \sqrt{\frac{\chi^2}{n}}$ then obtain T by $T_r = \frac{r\sqrt{n-2}}{\sqrt{1-r^2}}$. With known T , convert T to Z by $T = 1.15X$ then $Z = (1.15T - 1.64) + 1.40$. With known Z , obtain $F(Z)$ by $F(Z) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-\sqrt{\pi}(\beta_1 Z^5 + \beta_2 Z^3 + \beta_3 Z))}$ where $\beta_1 = 0.0004406$, $\beta_2 = 0.0418198$, and $\beta_3 = 0.90000000$. Obtain pValue by $1 - F(Z)$.

Chi square	Z	F(Z)	pValue = 1 - F(Z)
1.00	1.00	0.8415	0.1585
1.20	1.10	0.8636	0.1364
1.30	1.14	0.8732	0.1268
1.40	1.18	0.8820	0.1180
1.50	1.22	0.8901	0.1099
1.64	1.28	0.9003	0.0997
1.76	1.33	0.9082	0.0918
1.88	1.37	0.9154	0.0846
2.00	1.41	0.9220	0.0780
2.12	1.46	0.9280	0.0720
2.24	1.50	0.9335	0.0665
2.36	1.54	0.9385	0.0615
2.48	1.57	0.9431	0.0569
2.60	1.61	0.9474	0.0526
2.72	1.65	0.9513	0.0487
2.84	1.69	0.9549	0.0451
2.96	1.72	0.9582	0.0418
3.08	1.75	0.9613	0.0387

3.20	1.79	0.9641	0.0359
3.32	1.82	0.9667	0.0333
3.44	1.85	0.9692	0.0308
3.56	1.89	0.9714	0.0286
3.68	1.92	0.9735	0.0265
3.80	1.95	0.9754	0.0246
3.92	1.98	0.9772	0.0228
4.04	2.01	0.9788	0.0212
4.16	2.04	0.9803	0.0197
4.28	2.07	0.9817	0.0183
4.40	2.10	0.9831	0.0169
4.52	2.13	0.9843	0.0157
4.64	2.15	0.9854	0.0146
4.76	2.18	0.9864	0.0136
4.88	2.21	0.9874	0.0126
5.00	2.24	0.9883	0.0117
5.12	2.26	0.9892	0.0108
5.24	2.29	0.9899	0.0101
5.36	2.32	0.9907	0.0093
5.48	2.34	0.9913	0.0087
5.60	2.37	0.9919	0.0081
5.72	2.39	0.9925	0.0075
5.84	2.42	0.9931	0.0069
5.96	2.44	0.9936	0.0064
6.08	2.47	0.9940	0.0060
6.20	2.49	0.9945	0.0055
6.32	2.51	0.9949	0.0051
6.44	2.54	0.9952	0.0048
6.56	2.56	0.9956	0.0044
6.68	2.58	0.9959	0.0041
6.80	2.61	0.9962	0.0038
6.92	2.63	0.9965	0.0035
7.04	2.65	0.9967	0.0033
7.16	2.68	0.9970	0.0030
7.28	2.70	0.9972	0.0028
7.40	2.72	0.9974	0.0026
7.52	2.74	0.9976	0.0024
7.64	2.76	0.9978	0.0022
7.76	2.79	0.9979	0.0021
7.88	2.81	0.9981	0.0019
8.00	2.83	0.9982	0.0018
8.12	2.85	0.9984	0.0016
8.24	2.87	0.9985	0.0015
8.36	2.89	0.9986	0.0014
8.48	2.91	0.9987	0.0013
8.60	2.93	0.9988	0.0012
8.72	2.95	0.9989	0.0011
8.84	2.97	0.9990	0.0010
8.96	2.99	0.9990	0.0010
9.08	3.01	0.9991	0.0009
9.20	3.03	0.9992	0.0008

9.32	3.05	0.9992	0.0008
9.44	3.07	0.9993	0.0007
9.56	3.09	0.9994	0.0006
9.68	3.11	0.9994	0.0006
9.80	3.13	0.9994	0.0006
9.92	3.15	0.9995	0.0005
10.04	3.17	0.9995	0.0005
10.16	3.19	0.9996	0.0004
10.28	3.21	0.9996	0.0004
10.40	3.22	0.9996	0.0004
10.52	3.24	0.9997	0.0003
10.64	3.26	0.9997	0.0003
10.76	3.28	0.9997	0.0003
10.88	3.30	0.9997	0.0003
11.00	3.32	0.9998	0.0002
11.12	3.33	0.9998	0.0002
11.24	3.35	0.9998	0.0002
11.36	3.37	0.9998	0.0002
11.48	3.39	0.9998	0.0002
11.60	3.41	0.9998	0.0002
11.72	3.42	0.9998	0.0002
11.84	3.44	0.9999	0.0001
11.96	3.46	0.9999	0.0001
12.08	3.48	0.9999	0.0001
12.20	3.49	0.9999	0.0001
12.32	3.51	0.9999	0.0001
12.44	3.53	0.9999	0.0001
12.56	3.54	0.9999	0.0001
12.68	3.56	0.9999	0.0001
12.80	3.58	0.9999	0.0001
12.92	3.59	0.9999	0.0001
13.04	3.61	0.9999	0.0001
13.16	3.63	0.9999	0.0001
13.28	3.64	0.9999	0.0001
13.40	3.66	1.0000	0.0000
13.52	3.68	1.0000	0.0000
13.64	3.69	1.0000	0.0000
13.76	3.71	1.0000	0.0000
13.88	3.73	1.0000	0.0000
14.00	3.74	1.0000	0.0000

APPENDIX 4
pValue from F Statistic

First convert F to T by $F = T^2$. To express T in terms of F then $T = \sqrt{F}$. With known T, convert T to Z by $T = 1.15X$ then $Z = (1.15T - 1.64) + 1.40$. In the second step, find f(Z) by

$$F(Z) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp\left(-\sqrt{\pi}\left(\beta_1 Z^5 + \beta_2 Z^3 + \beta_3 Z\right)\right)}$$

where $\beta_1 = 0.0004406$, $\beta_2 = 0.0418198$, and $\beta_3 =$

0.90000000. Obtain pValue by $1 - F(Z)$.

F	T	Z	F(Z)	pValue = 1 - F(Z)
1.00	1.00	0.91	0.8187	0.1813
1.10	1.05	0.97	0.8332	0.1668
1.20	1.10	1.02	0.8463	0.1537
1.30	1.14	1.07	0.8582	0.1418
1.40	1.18	1.12	0.8691	0.1309
1.50	1.22	1.17	0.8790	0.1210
1.60	1.26	1.21	0.8882	0.1118
1.70	1.30	1.26	0.8965	0.1035
1.80	1.34	1.30	0.9042	0.0958
1.90	1.38	1.35	0.9113	0.0887
2.00	1.41	1.39	0.9178	0.0822
2.10	1.45	1.43	0.9238	0.0762
2.20	1.48	1.47	0.9293	0.0707
2.30	1.52	1.50	0.9344	0.0656
2.40	1.55	1.54	0.9392	0.0608
2.50	1.58	1.58	0.9435	0.0565
2.60	1.61	1.61	0.9476	0.0524
2.70	1.64	1.65	0.9513	0.0487
2.80	1.67	1.68	0.9548	0.0452
2.90	1.70	1.72	0.9580	0.0420
3.00	1.73	1.75	0.9610	0.0390

3.10	1.76	1.78	0.9638	0.0362
3.20	1.79	1.82	0.9664	0.0336
3.30	1.82	1.85	0.9688	0.0312
3.40	1.84	1.88	0.9710	0.0290
3.50	1.87	1.91	0.9730	0.0270
3.60	1.90	1.94	0.9749	0.0251
3.70	1.92	1.97	0.9767	0.0233
3.80	1.95	2.00	0.9784	0.0216
3.90	1.97	2.03	0.9799	0.0201
4.00	2.00	2.06	0.9813	0.0187
4.10	2.02	2.09	0.9827	0.0173
4.20	2.05	2.12	0.9839	0.0161
4.30	2.07	2.14	0.9850	0.0150
4.40	2.10	2.17	0.9861	0.0139
4.50	2.12	2.20	0.9871	0.0129
4.60	2.14	2.23	0.9880	0.0120
4.70	2.17	2.25	0.9889	0.0111
4.80	2.19	2.28	0.9897	0.0103
4.90	2.21	2.31	0.9904	0.0096
5.00	2.24	2.33	0.9911	0.0089